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Culture and Space in the Cinema of Yeşim Ustaoglu¹

Yeşim Ustaoglu Sinemasında Kültür ve Mekân

ABSTRACT

Yeşim Ustaoglu is regarded as one of the most significant directors of New Turkish Cinema. As a trained architect, she incorporates spatial configurations in her films that contain numerous cultural elements revealing information about the identities of her characters. For this reason, within the scope of this study, Ustaoglu's feature-length fiction films are examined under the cultural components classified by Bozkurt Güvenç. In order to evaluate the interaction between culture and space, the selected sample consists of the director's films *The Trace* (1994), *Journey to the Sun* (1999), *Waiting for the Clouds* (2004), *Pandora's Box* (2008), *Somewhere in Between* (2012), and *Clair Obscur* (2016). The elements used in the analysis of these films are categorized through tables, and the recurring spatial patterns are evaluated in light of this data. In assessing these films, ten phenomena listed under the section titled "Culture" are employed: Language; Sources (Customs / Traditions); People / Individual - Person; Family, Lineage, Kinship; Health and Disease; Art, Knowledge and Education; Places of Settlement; Production - Consumption; Religion - State - Governance; and lastly, Environment. The findings of the study demonstrate that the architect-director actively employs all of these cultural components in her feature-length fiction films. The most frequently used spaces in her films are residential interiors and urban settings. These elements of the built environment are often complemented by natural elements such as mountains, the sea, waves, and mist, and such spatial uses recur across many of her films. It is anticipated that this study will contribute to the existing literature on the relationship between cinema and architecture from a cultural perspective.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Architecture, Space, Cinema, Culture, Yeşim Ustaoglu.

ÖZET

Yeşim Ustaoglu, Yeni Türkiye Sineması'nın en önemli yönetmenlerinden biri olarak kabul edilmektedir. Aynı zamanda yüksek mimar olan yönetmen, filmlerinde karakterlerin kimliklerine dair önemli ipuçları barındıran mekânsal kurgular aracılığıyla çok sayıda kültürel öğeyi görünür kılmaktadır. Bu nedenle bu çalışma kapsamında, Ustaoglu'nun uzun metrajlı kurmaca filmleri Bozkurt Güvenç'in kültür sınıflandırmasında yer alan kültür bileşenleri çerçevesinde incelenmiştir. Kültür-mekân etkileşimini değerlendirebilmek amacıyla seçilen örneklem, yönetmenin *İz* (1994), *Güneşe Yolculuk* (1999), *Bulutları Beklerken* (2004), *Pandora'nın Kutusu* (2008), *Araf* (2012) ve *Tereddüt* (2016) adlı filmlerinden oluşmaktadır. Filmlerin analizinde kullanılan öğeler tablolar aracılığıyla sınıflandırılmış; filmlerde tekrar eden mekânsal örüntüler bu veriler ışığında değerlendirilmiştir. Filmlerin incelenmesinde, "Kültür" başlığı altında sıralanan on olgu temel alınmıştır: Dil; Kaynaklar (Gelenek ve Görenekler); İnsan / Birey; Aile, Soy ve Akrabalık; Sağlık ve Hastalık; Sanat, Bilgi ve Eğitim; Yerleşim Yerleri; Üretim - Tüketim; Din - Devlet - Yönetim; ve son olarak Çevre. Yapılan analiz sonucunda, mimar kimliğine sahip yönetmenin uzun metrajlı kurmaca filmlerinde söz konusu başlıkların tamamını aktif biçimde kullandığı görülmüştür. Yönetmenin en sık başvurduğu mekânlar konut içleri ve kentsel alanlardır. Bu yapay çevre unsurlarına dağlar, deniz, dalgalar ve sis gibi doğal öğeler eşlik etmekte; söz konusu mekânsal kullanımlar birçok filmde tekrar eden bir özellik göstermektedir. Çalışmanın, sinema ve mimarlık ilişkisine kültürel bir perspektiften yaklaşarak mevcut literatüre katkı sağlayacağı düşünülmektedir.

Keywords: Mimarlık, Mekân, Sinema, Kültür, Yeşim Ustaoglu.

¹ This article is partially derived from the first author's master's thesis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Architecture is the discipline of designing and organizing all forms of physical environments, from shelter to urban life. It is inherently related to science, art, technique, and human existence. Auguste Perret defines architecture as “the art of organizing space.” Beyond the three-dimensionality of a structure, space constitutes a fourth dimension shaped by human relations and interactions with objects. Victor Hugo likens architecture to a book written in stone, arguing that before the invention of the printing press, history could be read through buildings. Architecture renders visible the symbols born of traditions and reflects collective thought. Similarly, Henri Lefebvre emphasizes the traces and signs embedded in space, suggesting that space becomes a form of writing in which the body leaves clues and inscribes its movements. In this broad sense, space is one of the modes of existence of social relations and forms part not only of biological life but also of societal existence (Akyıldız, 2012; Asiliskender, 2004; Lefebvre, 2002).

According to Deleuze and Guattari, space is participation in a continual process of becoming; it is life itself. Spaces function as centers of lived experience where traditions, habits, and societal values are encoded. Norberg-Schulz similarly argues that space is shaped by culture; styles, habits, and relationships with nature influence its formation, while societies objectify their culture through spatial production. These forms gain meaning only for those who inhabit that culture (Asiliskender, 2004). Just as buildings and cities preserve images of culture and specific ways of life, cinema illuminates the cultural archaeology of both the time in which it is produced and the time it represents. Both architecture and cinema define the qualities of existential space and construct experiential settings for human life (Pallasmaa, 2006). Since every film defines a space and culture shapes space, it can be argued that all films contain cultural signs. Therefore, studies of culture space interaction contribute not only to cinema but also to architectural and cultural theory.

From its emergence in the twentieth century, cinema has developed in close relationship with older disciplines such as architecture. Cinema conveys events and situations not only through narrative but also through music, editing, and spatial organization. Unlike other arts, its dimensions of movement and time position it particularly close to architecture. The relationship between cinema and architecture extends beyond architecture serving merely as a backdrop; rather, cinema reproduces the dominant perception of urban space through its own techniques, transforming it into cinematic space. Cinematic space is the reconfiguration of three-dimensional architectural space into a two-dimensional visual plane through cinematic language, regaining its third dimension through movement. Architectural space in film cannot be separated from aesthetic concerns or from the political and cultural context of the society in which it is produced. Scholars such as Anthony Vidler and Richard Ingersoll argue that architecture maintains one of the most complex relationships with film and that it is the hidden subject of nearly every film. Cinema is thus one of the most powerful visual media through which architecture can be expressed (Köseoğlu, 2013).

Culture encompasses everything individuals acquire through interaction with society and transmit to future generations. It is learned, historical, continuous, social, changing, and integrative. In the context of human environment interaction, culture plays a decisive role in shaping the physical environment; housing, settlements, and the built environment reflect cultural values. Space is therefore not merely a passive physical container but a socially produced text, continually reshaped by human actions. What transforms a physical volume into space is the meaning attributed to it through lived experience and collective memory. In cinema, space is re-experienced by actors and audiences alike, and editing techniques that connect cinematic spaces have inspired architectural thinking. Ultimately, since the beginning of film history, cinema and architecture have mutually influenced one another. In film, space symbolizes social status and character identity, functioning not only as the setting of narrative but also as a representational tool. Space is thus an indispensable expressive element of cinema and one of the filmmaker’s most significant narrative instruments (Köseoğlu, 2013).

2. CULTURE

Among at least 164 different definitions of the concept of culture, the most frequently cited is arguably that of Marx: culture is everything created by human beings in contrast to what is created by nature. In fact, apart from animate and inanimate nature, everything that is the product of human effort and labor carries cultural meaning and value. From this perspective, everything whether written or printed, oral or musical, good or bad, beautiful or ugly, right or wrong can be examined as a cultural element and symbol (Güvenç, 2003).

Furthermore, according to Güvenç's study on the characteristics and principles of culture:

- Culture is learned.
- Culture is historical and continuous.
- Culture is social.
- Culture is a system of ideal or idealized rules.
- Culture fulfills needs and provides satisfaction.
- Culture changes.
- Culture is integrative.

Culture is an abstraction (Güvenç, 2003).

Figure 1. Culture Schema (Güvenç, 2003)

Below, as presented in this schema, the intended meanings of each category are explained.

1. Language: This category refers to spaces, situations, and narratives in which traces of the official language adopted or concealed by the state, as well as the mother tongues used by communities, can be identified.

2. Sources (Customs / Traditions): This category includes spaces where written and oral history both official and alternative becomes visible in contemporary life practices. It encompasses all sources of knowledge reflected in present-day living, along with customs, traditions, and habits that define cultural identity. Children's games and leisure activities are also evaluated within this scope.

3. People / Individual Person: This category examines spaces shaped by individuals' positions within society. It includes social networks formed across different segments of society and situations where socially accepted schemas, norms, standards, and unwritten rules can be observed through individuals. It also covers repeated systems of action and behavior that define social life. Furthermore, it addresses worldview, self-image, lifestyle, values, and ideals referring to spaces where individuals reflect their identities. Cultural values and norms imposed by society and institutions may be reinterpreted by the individual and transformed into personal identity, and the ideals emerging from this identity construction are also examined within this framework.

4. Family, Lineage, Kinship: This category defines spaces where all knowledge belonging to and acquired from the family is transmitted. It includes family structure and roles, kinship and lineage relations, family

size, lifestyle, worldview, social attitudes, self-image, expectations, and hopes. These elements reveal how the family shapes the individual's identity and social positioning.

5. Health and Disease (including Nutrition and Death): This category includes spaces associated with nutrition, health, and illness as organized by society and its institutions. Both illness and death whether natural or unnatural are considered important sources of information about social life, as the ways people experience illness and death provide insight into the lives they have lived. Hospital culture and religious and social rituals following death define a broader funeral culture. Sports are also examined under this heading due to their relation to health.

6. Art, Knowledge and Education: Defined as the organization of meaning and communication, this category includes spaces where systematically produced and practiced sciences, art forms, and the tools that enable the production and dissemination of knowledge are identified. Education may be delivered through official institutions or transmitted orally between individuals. Individuals may interpret the education they receive positively or consciously develop behaviors contrary to it.

7. Places of Settlement: This category refers to the built environment as a system of settlements composed of fixed, semi-fixed, and changeable elements. It includes all measurable and institutionalized knowledge related to human-made environments. Housing, in particular, encompasses norms of use, basic functions and meanings, the individual's functional and emotional relationship with the dwelling, housing experiences, and the reflection of official and unofficial institutions within domestic space.

8. Production - Consumption: Every social and cultural system must consume various goods primarily food in order to survive. These goods must be produced, transported, and distributed. Economics and technology regulate and develop these production consumption relations. Technology supports production and consumption through energy systems, transportation, communication, technical control, and standardization. From agricultural laborers to highly specialized experts, members of the cultural system participate in economic and technological activities or supporting service sectors to sustain their lives, (Güvenç, 2003).

9. Religion - State - Governance: This category includes spaces related to religions adopted or rejected by individuals, official state institutions, areas influenced by state authorities, and spaces where the positive or negative effects of political leadership on society can be observed.

10. Environment: This category examines both natural and built environments, including climate, topography, natural patterns and materials, cultural and historical context, human-made fabric, and norms of environmental and spatial use. It addresses all characteristics shaping environmental identity, as well as the spaces where individuals realize themselves, establish close relationships, and reflect their identities through patterns of spatial use and life intensity.

3. YEŞİM USTAOĞLU

Yeşim Ustaoğlu was born on November 18, 1960, in Sarıkamış, Kars. She completed her undergraduate education in the Department of Architecture at Karadeniz Technical University between 1977 and 1981. After graduation, she pursued a master's degree in the Rölöve - Restoration Program within the Department of Architecture at Yıldız Technical University in Istanbul. In 1985, she completed her master's studies with a thesis titled "*An Examination of the Hagios Anargyros (Sivişli) Church and Its Surrounding Fabric in Güzelyurt (Gelveri).*"

During this period, she both worked professionally and began directing short films. After making four short films, she directed her first feature-length film. Nearly all of her films have received awards at numerous national and international festivals (Köseoğlu, 2013).

Table 1. List of Films Directed by Yeşim Ustaoğlu by Genre

Short films	Documentary	Feature film
To Catch a Moment, 1984	Life on Their Shoulders, 2004	The Trace, 1994
Magnafantagna, 1987		Journey to the Sun, 1999
Duet, 1990		Waiting for the Clouds, 2004
Hotel, 1992		Pandora's Box, 2008
		Somewhere in Between, 2012
		Clair Obscur, 2016

The ten short, documentary, and fiction films directed by Yeşim Ustaoglu to date are listed in the table above. However, this study focuses specifically on the director's feature-length fiction films.

4. RESULTS

Within the scope of this study, Yeşim Ustaoglu's feature-length fiction films have been examined under the cultural components classified by Bozkurt Güvenç. In order to evaluate the interaction between culture and space, the selected sample consists of the director's films *The Trace* (1994), *Journey to the Sun* (1999), *Waiting for the Clouds* (2004), *Pandora's Box* (2008), *Somewhere in Between* (2012), and *Clair Obscur* (2016).

The elements used in the analysis of these films were categorized through tables, and recurring spatial patterns were evaluated in light of these data. In assessing the films, the ten cultural components listed in the Culture section were employed: Language; Sources (Customs / Traditions); People / Individual - Person; Family, Lineage, Kinship; Health and Disease; Art, Knowledge and Education; Places of Settlement; Production - Consumption; Religion - State - Governance; and finally, Environment.

It is considered that the environment presented in these films provides the viewer with clues for understanding the characters. In other words, the environment reflects the personalities of the film's protagonists. The visually presented setting allows the audience to form initial impressions about the characters. By observing the house in which a character lives, it is possible to understand whether the setting is urban or rural, whether the character lives alone, whether they are wealthy or poor, and what their social position might be.

The analyses conducted within this framework demonstrate that residential spaces are the places with which individuals establish the strongest identification. In parallel with the literature, the dwelling spaces most strongly associated with individual identity were examined in detail, and the cultural significance of housing was emphasized. Across all the films analyzed, a common finding is that the type of dwelling depicted provides insight into the social status of the family portrayed in the narrative.

4.1. The Trace, 1994

In *The Trace*, it is observed that space is constructed primarily at the urban scale, and Istanbul is represented as an uncanny environment that generates negative emotions. Urban spaces are designed to reflect the psychological states of the characters, and the film's sense of reality is deliberately fragmented. The relationship between space and cultural components is interpreted through the individual's tense and conflicted relationship with the city. Below, the cultural components are presented according to spaces and narrative elements:

Table 2. Cultural Components of the *Trace*

	Spaces	Narrative
Language	Istanbul	A distanced language reflecting official institutions.
Sources (Customs / Traditions)	Family home	Traditional family order, male dominance, female passivity.
People / Individual - Person	Wandering in the city	Uncanny streets, a labyrinthine structure, feelings of loneliness and loss.
Family, Lineage, Kinship	Family home	Photographs and personal belongings; the absence of a father figure.
Health and Disease	Interior spaces	Suicide, trauma, psychological breakdown.
Art, Knowledge and Education	Official and personal archives	Obstruction of access to information.
Places of Settlement	Istanbul, apartment flat	Alienation in the city.
Production - Consumption	Workspaces	Economic uncertainty.
Religion - State - Governance	Official institutions	Political pressure.
Environment	Urban fabric of Istanbul	Spatial confinement, the subconscious, amnesia, traces and remnants within the city, historic structures.

4.2. Journey to the Sun, 1999

In *Journey to the Sun*, the geography in which the film is set establishes strong ties with its culture and people. By using real locations, the film demonstrates how space is socially reproduced and how ideology and culture are reconstructed through these spaces. The reproduced spaces and cultural elements appear as expressions of human identity within the film. The identity-forming role of space becomes visible through individuals' experiences of belonging, displacement, and relocation.

Below, the cultural components are presented according to spaces and narrative elements:

Table 3. Cultural Components of *Journey to the Sun*

	Spaces	Narrative
Language	Istanbul, the Southeast, villages, police station, public spaces	The dominance of Turkish; Kurdish spoken in Istanbul's <i>gecekondu</i> (informal housing) neighborhood and in Berzan's village; the use of official language in public institutions and spaces.
Sources (Customs / Traditions)	Istanbul, the Southeast	Traditional music and dance; burial and mourning rituals.
People / Individual - Person	Mehmet's rented room, prison cell, the journey	Misidentification; name and physical appearance as markers of identity; the individual's vulnerability before the state; friendship; guilt and innocence; transformation of identity.
Family, Lineage, Kinship	Istanbul and villages	Separation from family; funerals; non-biological brotherhood bonds; displaced families.
Health and Disease	Prison, houses, morgue	Physical violence; trauma; the effects of war on the body; death.
Art, Knowledge and Education	Istanbul and villages	Vocational training; control of newspaper distribution; traditional music and dance; cassette culture in the city.
Places of Settlement	Istanbul city center and gecekondu neighborhood, Kurdish villages	Internal migration; forced village evacuations; alienation in the city.
Production - Consumption	<i>Gecekondu</i> surroundings	Construction sites; unemployment; lower-class labor; poverty.
Religion - State - Governance	Police station, Prison, Government offices, Military checkpoints	Nation-state identity politics, state violence, political oppression, the right to burial.
Environment	Evacuated villages, the road	Destruction, the politicization of space.

4.3. Waiting for the Clouds, 2004

In *Waiting for the Clouds*, spaces function as carriers of memory. They are constructed not only as representations of the present moment but also of the past and of an absent present. It is observed that the main characters symbolize both past and present, while the spaces render these temporal ruptures visible. The film employs space as a container of both individual and collective memory.

Below, the cultural components are presented through their spatial and narrative associations:

Table 4. Cultural Components of *Waiting for the Clouds*

	Spaces	Narrative
Language	Black Sea region in Turkey, Highland, Greece	Turkish is generally spoken in the Black Sea region; Greek (Rumca) is spoken in the highlands and in Greece. Language functions as a carrier of identity, connected to population exchange and hidden identity.
Sources (Customs / Traditions)	Black Sea region, rural settlement in Greece	Traditional Black Sea way of life; patterns of human relationships in the rural settlement in Greece.
People / Individual - Person	Houses	Ayşe/Eleni's house and the journey route reflect dual identity, a suppressed past, confrontation, and belonging.
Family, Lineage, Kinship	Family home, neighborhood	Eleni's reunion with her brother; forced assimilation; Ayşe's bond with her neighbor's son.
Health and Disease	Domestic care space	Elderly care; memory and the body; trauma and psychological burdens.
Art, Knowledge and Education	School, letters, and photographs	Official history represented by the state school, contrasted with letters and photographs as elements of oral culture and the preservation of hidden knowledge.
Places of Settlement	Black Sea region	Houses settled along steep slopes; dense rural settlement patterns and highland houses; mountainous geography.
Production - Consumption	Village gardens and production areas	Rural production; traditional labor; collective work in everyday life.
Religion - State - Governance	Mosque, Church, State school, Hospital	Religious conversion; nation-state policies; population exchange; minority identity; census practices.
Environment	Misty mountains, forests, and sea of the Black Sea	The cloud metaphor; fog and ambiguity; forgetting and remembering; representations of confrontation, loss, and reunion.

4.4. Pandora's Box, 2008

In *Pandora's Box*, the narrative moves back and forth between provincial and urban spaces. Both residential spaces that define personal domains and public spaces are used intensively throughout the film. The representation of the city functions as a tool that enables an analysis of all the main characters. Public spaces, in particular, play a decisive role as sites of conflict and tension arising from interpersonal encounters.

Below, the cultural components are presented through their spatial and narrative associations:

Table 5. Cultural Components of *Pandora's Box*

	Spaces	Narrative
Language	Residences in Istanbul	Intergenerational communication breakdown; loss of language and memory due to illness; silence.
Sources (Customs / Traditions)	Mountain house in the Black Sea region	Elderly care as a family responsibility; conflict between traditional values and modern life.
People / Individual - Person	All residences belonging to the mother and children	Individualization and loneliness in Istanbul versus contact with nature in the village; old age, loss of identity, confrontation with the past; tension between individualization and belonging.
Family, Lineage, Kinship	Houses and the journey	Fragmented family structure; responsibility and conscience in caregiving; intergenerational conflict and lack of communication.
Health and Disease	Hospital and in-home care spaces	Illness-related memory loss; old age and the ethics of care; debates around the body, identity, and family relationships.
Art, Knowledge and Education	Urban living spaces and university	Modern cultural environment; educational settings of the younger generation; the difference between experiential knowledge transmitted across generations and modern knowledge acquired through formal education.
Places of Settlement	Istanbul (gated communities) and rural settlements in the Black Sea region	Urban-rural dichotomy; contrast between spatially confined urban life and isolated natural village life; spatial alienation, belonging, migration, and return. The question "Where is my mountain?" A search for roots, belonging, and identity.
Production - Consumption	Village, city, and domestic interiors	Traditional production in the village; work and consumption in the city; invisible domestic labor within the home.
Religion - State - Governance	Health system	Official state health institutions.
Environment	Black Sea region and Istanbul	Nature, roots, belonging, memory; enclosed and compressed spaces in the city.

4.5. Somewhere in Between, 2012

In *Somewhere in Between*, space is constructed not only within a cultural framework but also as a mode of thought. The roadside lodging facility along the highway is presented as a place where no one wishes to stay and which functions merely as a transient zone. Through this setting, the future aspirations of lower-income protagonists and the contradictions they experience in relation to these aspirations are rendered visible.

Below, the cultural components are presented through their spatial and narrative associations:

Table 6. Cultural Components of *Somewhere in Between*

	Spaces	Narrative
Language	Railway tracks, bus terminal	Silence; class-based and patriarchal discourse; a sense of repression.
Sources (Customs / Traditions)	Family home	Honor and prescribed roles of womanhood; expectations of marriage; social pressure and traditional norms.
People / Individual - Person	Zehra's private space within the home, the road	In-betweenness; the tension between adulthood and the role of a child within the family; guilt and the struggle for subjectivity.
Family, Lineage, Kinship	Family home	The invisible yet authoritarian father; the silent mother; intergenerational transmission of traditional roles.
Health and Disease	Hospital corridors	An unwanted and concealed pregnancy; social control over the body; trauma.
Art, Knowledge and Education	Workplace training and media	Transition from an educational environment to a work environment; the effort to gain visibility in the media; confrontation with social realities.
Places of Settlement	Province, highway, roadside rest facility	Center-periphery tension; spaces of transit and waiting; spatial confinement and the desire for escape.
Production - Consumption	Rest facility, kitchen, service area	Labor exploitation; precarious employment; class; conflicts between consumption and modernity.
Religion - State - Governance	Official institutions	Social and familial control through state institutions such as public hospitals; the biopolitical presence of the state; social morality; invisible oppressive power.
Environment	Highway, dark dwellings, industrial environment	Spatial confinement; pressure and the search for escape; stagnation and an existential state of limbo.

4.6. Clair Obscur, 2016

In *Clair Obscur*, two women from different social backgrounds come together in a therapy room. Their lives, marriages, relationships with their husbands, and the spaces accompanying these experiences are presented to the viewer. Once again, social status is emphasized through domestic spaces in which the husband acts as the rule-maker. In contrast, outside the home by the seaside, in the car, or at the Office the women are shown in spaces where they are able to be themselves.

Below, the cultural components are presented through their spatial and narrative associations:

Table 7. Cultural Components of *Clair Obscur*

	Spaces	Narrative
Language	Therapy room	Everyday conversations; silence; patriarchal language.
Sources (Customs / Traditions)	Elmas's house	Child marriage; patriarchal norms; honor and obedience; traditional female roles.
People / Individual - Person	Şehnaz's and Elmas's homes	Şehnaz's modern apartment versus Elmas's enclosed and controlled typical flat; loneliness and hesitation.
Family, Lineage, Kinship	Elmas's house	Elmas and her mother-in-law living in facing houses; forced marriage; surveillance; power relations between spouses; domestic violence; silence within the family.
Health and Disease	Hospital, home	Public hospital and therapy room; elderly care at home; trauma; sexual violence; control over the female body.
Art, Knowledge and Education	Professional environment	Class differences shaped by education; contrast between modern urban life and the province.
Places of Settlement	Metropolitan city and rural seaside settlement	Center-periphery conflict; spatial confinement; debates on escape and belonging.
Production - Consumption	Home and clinic	Invisible domestic labor; the hospital as a professional workplace; women's labor; economic dependence on men; class inequality.
Religion - State - Governance	Home - Public sphere	Official marriage and civil registration; legal marriage age; patriarchal order; the biopolitical framework of the state; social control.
Environment	Seaside	Closely built apartment blocks; modern detached houses; hospitals; long roads and waves; an atmosphere of melancholy.

5. CONCLUSION

All films in the world define a form of space; since culture constitutes space, it can be argued that cultural signs are present in every type of film. Research of this kind contributes not only to the concretization of the Culture space interaction in cinema, but also to cinema, architecture, and cultural theory. Theories discussed through examples become easier to understand, and ongoing debates can be sustained through new interpretations based on contemporary works.

Studies on space in Turkish Cinema over approximately the last twenty years are relatively recent when considered within the broader history of cinema–architecture interaction and architectural discourse. Gaps in the literature have been recognized and attempts have been made to fill them. Similarly, discussing the cinema-architecture relationship within the framework of Culture-space interaction aims to address an identified gap in the literature.

Within the scope of this study, the use of space in Yeşim Ustaoglu's films within New Turkish Cinema has been analyzed. It is important not only which cultural data the director conveys through space, but also how she accomplishes this that is, which tools she employs. For this reason, the conclusions of the study are addressed in three stages.

In the first stage, the spaces in Yeşim Ustaoglu's films *The Trace*, *Journey to the Sun*, *Waiting for the Clouds*, *Pandora's Box*, and *Somewhere in Between* were examined within the framework of cultural components, and the findings were evaluated collectively. This made it possible to analyze the director's overall spatial approach across her body of work. As a result of the analysis, the theoretical framework was discussed, and it was observed that each of the identified cultural components found correspondence in most of the director's films, thereby testing the validity of the hypothesis. It was determined that Yeşim Ustaoglu's film spaces are shaped by cultural components.

The second conclusion evaluates what types of spatial use the films exemplify within the definitions established under the heading Cinema-Space Interaction. The analysis revealed that all the films were shot in real locations. The use of existing spaces, examples of reconstructed spaces, and the functions of space within the narrative were assessed for each film individually. It was determined that in these films, space assumes a leading role, becomes identified with the characters, and functions as a carrier of the narrative.

The third conclusion aims to systematically identify the recurring elements used in Yeşim Ustaoglu's films. It was observed that architectural elements, design elements, and objects form a recurring language throughout all or most of the films. Architectural elements such as the road, the province, the city, the street, the door, and the window; design elements such as light, color, texture, boundary, framing, repetition, and perspective; and objects such as photographs, mass communication devices, and means of transportation are used consistently across the films.

Table 8. Architectural Elements, Design Elements and Objects in Yeşim Ustaoglu Films

		<i>The Trace</i>	<i>Journey to the Sun</i>	<i>Waiting for the Clouds</i>	<i>Pandora's Box</i>	<i>Somewhere in Between</i>	<i>Clair Obscur</i>
Architectural Elements	Road	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Periphery / Rural Areas	•	•	•	•	•	•
	City	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Street	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Stairs	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Door	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Window	•	•	•	•	•	•
Design Elements	Light	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Color	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Texture	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Boundary	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Framing	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Repetition	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Perspective	•	•	•	•	•	•
Objects	Mirror	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Photographs	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Mass Media	•	•	•	•	•	•
	Means of Transportation	•	•	•	•	•	•

In conclusion, in Yeşim Ustaoglu's feature-length fiction films, space is not merely a backdrop against which the narrative unfolds; rather, it emerges as a fundamental component through which culture, identity, status, and social relations are produced. The director's background in architectural education demonstrates that her use of space forms a conscious and coherent cinematic language. In the films examined, space assumes a decisive role as a tool that defines characters, renders social structures visible, and carries cultural memory. Addressing the relationship between cinema and architecture within the framework of Culture-space interaction fills a significant gap in the literature and enables new interpretations of New Turkish Cinema.

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